

Optical Measurement Technique for Supersonic Jet Noise Using Laser and Position-Sensitive Detector*

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Precise near-field measurement of supersonic jet noise is essential for understanding its generation mechanisms and for developing effective noise mitigation strategies. However, conventional microphones often interfere with both the acoustic field and the flow field due to their physical presence. To address this limitation, this study proposes a novel non-intrusive measurement technique that utilizes a laser beam and a position-sensitive detector (PSD) to simultaneously capture the sound pressure and direction of supersonic jet noise. The underlying principle involves detecting deflections in the laser beam induced by acoustic density fluctuations in the acoustic field. This paper presents the experimental setup and signal processing methodology used to extract sound pressure level (SPL) and direction-of-arrival (DOA) information from the PSD output signal. Validation experiments demonstrate excellent agreement between the proposed technique and conventional methods such as free-field microphones and sound intensity probes, confirming the technique's potential for aeroacoustic diagnostics in challenging or inaccessible environments.

Key Words: Acoustics, Supersonic Jet Noise, Sound Pressure Level, Optical Metrology, Laser Measurement

1. Introduction

Supersonic jet noise has been a topic of interest in aeronautical and astronautical engineering for several decades since it can cause several problems.¹⁾ In the case of a launch vehicle, as the supersonic exhaust jet impinges on a launch pad on the ground, the acoustic waves generated due to the jet impingement may cause malfunction of electronic and mechanical components of the payloads mounted on launch vehicles.²⁾ Supersonic jet noise is also pointed out as one of the major obstacles to the realization of second-generation civil supersonic transport since it can cause serious noise pollution to inhabitants of nearby residential areas.³⁾ For these reasons, high-precision acoustic measurements are crucial not only for understanding the underlying noise generation mechanisms but also for identifying dominant noise sources and developing effective noise mitigation strategies in aerospace applications.⁴⁾ However, conventional microphones are often limited in high-speed flow environments, as their physical presence can disturb both the acoustic field and the flow field.⁵⁾

In order to address this issue, various laser-based measurement techniques have been proposed as means of measuring supersonic jet noise from a distance.⁶⁻¹²⁾ However, as existing techniques primarily focus on measuring only

the sound pressure, this study proposes a novel method that enables simultaneous measurement of both sound pressure and direction by detecting laser beam deflection using a position-sensitive detector (PSD). This proposed technique (hereinafter referred to as laser measurement) is highly applicable for aeroacoustic diagnostics in harsh, confined, or otherwise inaccessible environments such as high-enthalpy supersonic jet flows or launch pad noise measurements, owing to its compact configuration and non-intrusive nature. In addition, this technique is expected to be particularly useful when used in combination with far-field acoustic measurement data obtained simultaneously by microphones, as it enables measuring both the sound pressure and direction in the near field of a supersonic jet.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 describes the experimental setup, including the jet facility and measurement apparatus. Section 3 explains the measurement methodology, covering the measurement principle and calculation methods for sound direction and sound pressure level. Section 4 details the development of sound calculation methods, such as deflective length estimation and ambient light compensation. Section 5 presents validation results for sound direction and sound pressure calculations. Section 6 concludes the paper.

2. Experimental Setup

2.1. Jet facility

The experiment was conducted using a jet facility at the Hypersonic and High-Enthalpy Wind Tunnel, located at the Kashiwa Campus of The University of Tokyo.¹³⁾ An ideally expanded Mach 1.8 jet and an over-expanded Mach 1.57 jet were generated using an axisymmetric convergent-divergent (CD) nozzle with an exit diameter of $D = 0.02$ m. The detailed experimental conditions are summarized in Table 1.

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Table 1. Experimental conditions.

Parameter	Ideally expanded jet	Over-expanded jet
Jet Mach number	1.8	1.57
Nozzle exit diameter, m	0.02	0.02
Stagnation pressure, MPa	0.573 ± 0.01	0.400 ± 0.01
Stagnation temperature, K	300 ± 10	300 ± 10
Nozzle pressure ratio	5.73	4.00
Reynolds number	1.5×10^6	1.5×10^6

Although the jet facility is not anechoic, sound-absorbing materials were applied to minimize sound reflections for acoustic measurements. Further details regarding the jet facility, nozzle geometry, and acoustic environment can be found in the previous research by Akamine et al.¹⁴⁾

2.2. Measurement apparatus

Figure 1 shows the optical measurement setup used in this study. A laser beam (wavelength: 632.8 nm) emitted from a 0.5 mW He-Ne laser system (25-LHP-213, Melles Griot) passes through a neutral-density filter (transmittance: 50%, PRO ND2, Kenko Tokina) to adjust its intensity. It is then focused by a plano-convex lens (focal length: 1.2 m, SLB-50-1200PM, OptoSigma), passes through the acoustic field near a supersonic jet, and enters a position-sensitive detector (PSD; C10443-04, Hamamatsu Photonics). With a position resolution of 4.2 μm , the PSD detects the centroid of the incident light on its light-receiving surface and outputs its coordinates (X, Z), as shown in Fig. 2.

The coordinate system is defined as follows: the x -axis is aligned with the jet centerline (downstream direction), the y -axis is the direction of the laser beam propagation, and the z -axis is the vertical direction from the jet axis to the laser beam. The origin (x, y, z) = (0, 0, 0) is defined at the center of the nozzle exit, as shown in Fig. 1. The location of the measurement point on the x - z plane is expressed as ($x/D, z/D$), where D is the diameter of the nozzle exit.

3. Measurement Methodology

3.1. Measurement principle

Acoustic waves propagate through a medium by causing pressure fluctuations that result in variations in the density of the medium.¹⁶⁾ Meanwhile, light is an electromagnetic wave described by Maxwell's equations, and it propagates through a medium based on its spatial distribution of relative permittivity ε ($= n^2$, where n is the refractive index).¹⁷⁾ Because the refractive index of gases depends on their density via the Gladstone–Dale relation, pressure fluctuations due to acoustic waves cause refractive index gradients, which deflect a traversing laser beam.¹⁸⁾ Therefore, this deflection can be used to infer the sound pressure distribution in a stationary ambient medium.

In this section, for analytical simplicity, the acoustic wave is assumed to be a plane wave propagating along the ξ -axis, as illustrated in Fig. 3. The corresponding density fluctuation at a point along the direction ξ and time t is given by

$$\rho(\xi, t) = \hat{\rho} \exp\{i(k\xi - \omega t)\}, \quad (1)$$

where $\hat{\rho}$ is the amplitude of the density fluctuation, i is the

Fig. 1. Schematic of the laser measurement setup.

 Fig. 2. Schlieren visualization of tonal noise from an over-expanded jet (left),¹⁵⁾ and centroid coordinates of incident light on the PSD (right).

imaginary unit, k is the wavenumber, and ω ($= 2\pi f$, with f being the frequency) is the angular frequency.

When a laser beam propagates along the y -axis and intersects the acoustic field, the spatial gradient of density ρ causes a deflection of the beam in the ξ -direction. The deflection angle θ can be approximated by the ray equation:

$$\theta \approx \int_{-\ell/2}^{\ell/2} \frac{G}{n} \cdot \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial \xi} dy \left(= \frac{G}{n} \cdot \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial \xi} \cdot \ell \right), \quad (2)$$

where ℓ is the path length of the laser beam within the acoustic field. The Gladstone–Dale constant G in Eq. (2) is defined as follows:

$$G = \frac{n - n_0}{\rho}, \quad (3)$$

representing the linear relationship between gas density and the refractive index relative to vacuum ($n_0 = 1$).¹⁹⁾

Fig. 3. Light beam deflection by a plane wave.

From the equation of state, the isentropic relationship between pressure p and density ρ is expressed as

$$\left. \frac{\partial p}{\partial \rho} \right|_s = c^2, \quad (4)$$

where c denotes the speed of sound. This derivative is taken under isentropic conditions, assuming that acoustic wave propagation occurs as an adiabatic process.²⁰⁾ Furthermore, the one-dimensional wave equation,

$$\frac{\partial^2 \rho}{\partial t^2} = c^2 \frac{\partial^2 \rho}{\partial \xi^2}, \quad (5)$$

can be factored as

$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + c \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} \right) \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} - c \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} \right) \rho = 0. \quad (6)$$

By substituting Eqs. (4) and (6) into Eq. (2), the deflection angle can be expressed in terms of the time derivative of the sound pressure as

$$\theta = \frac{G}{n} \cdot \frac{1}{c^3} \cdot \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} \cdot \ell. \quad (7)$$

Let $\Theta(f)$ and $P(f)$ denote the Fourier transforms of the time-domain deflection angle $\theta(t)$ and sound pressure $p(t)$, respectively. The Fourier transformation of the above equation yields the following relation:²¹⁾

$$P(f) = \frac{c^3 n}{i2\pi f G \ell} \Theta(f). \quad (8)$$

This equation forms the theoretical basis for estimating the sound pressure spectrum from the laser beam deflection angle in the frequency domain, under the assumptions of linear acoustics and plane wave propagation.

3.2. Sound calculation methods

The proposed laser measurement technique simultaneously estimates both the sound pressure and direction by analyzing the deflection of a laser beam induced by acoustic waves. The deflection angle quantifies the sound pressure level (SPL), while its orientation indicates the direction of arrival (DOA). This section outlines the computational procedure for converting laser beam deflection into these acoustic parameters.

 Fig. 4. Schlieren visualization of Mach waves generated from an ideally expanded jet (left),¹⁵⁾ and PCA-based detection of DOA (right).

3.2.1. Calculation of sound direction

The direction of arrival (DOA), defined as the angle φ (in degrees) between the positive x -axis and the direction from which the acoustic wave propagates (Fig. 4), is estimated from the deflection pattern of the laser beam. Specifically, principal component analysis (PCA), a standard technique for dimensionality reduction,²²⁾ is applied to the incident light coordinates (X, Z) on the PSD's light-receiving surface to identify the principal axis of maximum variance, which corresponds to the DOA.

In addition, to improve the reliability, the time-series signals of the PSD output coordinates (X, Z) were preprocessed using a Butterworth band-pass filter with a passband of 1–80 kHz. The lower cutoff frequency of 1 kHz was chosen based on prior validation of acoustic measurements at the jet facility,¹⁴⁾ while the upper cutoff of 80 kHz is determined by the Nyquist criterion, given the 160 kHz sampling rate of the PSD.

3.2.2. Calculation of sound pressure level

The laser beam displacement $s(t)$ on the PSD's light-receiving surface is calculated from the time-dependent coordinates (X, Z) as:

$$s(t) = X(t) \cos\left(\frac{\varphi}{180}\pi\right) + Z(t) \sin\left(\frac{\varphi}{180}\pi\right), \quad (9)$$

where φ is the average DOA within the frequency range of 1–80 kHz, as described in Sect. 3.2.1. The deflection angle $\theta(t)$ of the laser beam is then obtained by:²³⁾

$$\theta(t) = \arctan \frac{s(t)}{D_y}, \quad (10)$$

where $D_y = 4.4$ m is the distance from the measurement point to the PSD along the y -axis, as shown in Fig. 1.

The deflection signal $\theta(t)$ is segmented into N_{block} blocks, each consisting of N samples, denoted by $\theta_b(t_\alpha)$. A fast Fourier transform (FFT) is then applied to each block to compute the root-mean-square (RMS) sound pressure $\bar{P}(f_\beta)$:

$$\bar{P}(f_\beta) = \frac{1}{N_{\text{block}}} \sum_{b=0}^{N_{\text{block}}} \left| 2 \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{c^3 n}{i2\pi f_\beta G \ell} \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{W}} \cdot \frac{1}{N} \text{FFT} \{w(t_\alpha) \cdot \theta_b(t_\alpha)\} (f_\beta) \right|, \quad (11)$$

where $t_\alpha = \alpha \delta t$ ($\alpha = 0, \dots, N-1$; $\delta t = 1/f_s$), and $f_\beta = \beta \delta f$ ($\beta = 0, \dots, N-1$; $\delta f = f_s/N$), with f_s being the sampling rate. The vertical bars $|\cdot|$ denote the absolute value, the factor of 2 accounts for the single-sided spectrum, and $1/\sqrt{2}$ converts the amplitude to an RMS value. The term

Fig. 5. Collimated laser beam passing through spherical waves.

$c^3 n / (i 2 \pi f_\beta \bar{G} L)$ originates from the theoretical relationship between the laser beam deflection angle and the sound pressure, as described in Eq. (8). Here, \bar{L} is the path length of the portion where the laser beam is actually deflected by the acoustic waves, referred to as the deflective length in this study; see Sect. 4.1 for details. The function $w(t_\alpha)$ represents the Hanning window, applied to suppress spectral leakage. The factor $1/\sqrt{W}$ compensates for the window-induced energy reduction, where W is the mean-square value of the Hanning window:

$$W = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{\alpha=0}^{N-1} w(t_\alpha)^2 = \frac{3}{8}. \quad (12)$$

A normalization factor of $1/N$ in Eq. (11) is introduced because the amplitude of the f_β Hz component is defined as $1/N \cdot \text{FFT}\{\theta(t_\alpha)\}(f_\beta)$, as shown in the following equation:

$$\theta(t_\alpha) = \text{IFFT}\{\text{FFT}(\theta)\} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{\beta=0}^{N-1} \text{FFT}\{\theta(t_\alpha)\}(f_\beta) e^{i 2 \pi f_\beta t_\alpha}, \quad (13)$$

where IFFT denotes the inverse fast Fourier transform.

The sound pressure level (SPL) is calculated from the RMS sound pressure signal $\bar{P}(f_\beta)$ as follows:

$$\text{SPL}(f_\beta) = 20 \log_{10} \frac{\bar{P}(f_\beta)}{p_{\text{ref}}} + C_{\text{AL}}, \quad (14)$$

where $p_{\text{ref}} = 2 \times 10^{-5}$ Pa is the standard reference sound pressure. The term C_{AL} is a correction factor accounting for the influence of ambient light, as described in Sect. 4.2.

The overall sound pressure level (OASPL) is obtained by integrating the SPL over the frequency range 1–80 kHz:

$$\text{OASPL} = 10 \log_{10} \left\{ \sum_{1\text{k} \leq f_\beta \leq 80\text{k}} 10^{\text{SPL}(f_\beta)/10} \right\}. \quad (15)$$

Both background noise and atmospheric attenuation were negligible due to the high signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) and the short source-to-laser distance, and were therefore not considered in this calculation.

 Fig. 6. Amplitude of laser beam deflection angle as a function of ℓ .

4. Development of Sound Calculation Methods

4.1. Estimation of deflective length

As an initial assumption, the supersonic jet noise is approximated as a spherical wave emitted from a point-like sound source, to simplify the analysis of wavefront curvature and amplitude decay. The density fluctuation of the spherical wave at a point (ξ, y) and time t is

$$\rho_{\text{spherical}}(\xi, y, t) = \hat{\rho} \frac{\exp\{i(k\sqrt{\xi^2 + y^2} - \omega t)\}}{\sqrt{\xi^2 + y^2}}, \quad (16)$$

where $\hat{\rho}$ denotes the amplitude, i is the imaginary unit, k is the wavenumber, ω is the angular frequency, and $\sqrt{\xi^2 + y^2}$ represents the distance from the sound source to a wavefront (i.e., the arc radius r), as illustrated in Fig. 5.

By substituting the above expression into the integral of Eq. (2) and taking the absolute value, the amplitude of the laser beam deflection angle induced by the spherical wave can be obtained as follows:

$$|\theta| \approx \left| \int_{-\frac{\ell}{2}}^{\frac{\ell}{2}} \frac{G}{n} \cdot \frac{\partial \rho_{\text{spherical}}}{\partial \xi} dy \right|. \quad (17)$$

Here, the distance from the sound source to the laser beam varies depending on the transverse position ξ within the laser beam cross-section, since the laser used in the measurement is a collimated beam with a beam width B_w of 2.12×10^{-3} m. Therefore, $|\theta|$ is averaged over $\xi \in [d - B_w/2, d + B_w/2]$, and the resulting average deflection angle $|\bar{\theta}|$ is given by:

$$|\bar{\theta}| \approx \frac{1}{B_w} \int_{d - \frac{B_w}{2}}^{d + \frac{B_w}{2}} \left| \int_{-\frac{\ell}{2}}^{\frac{\ell}{2}} \frac{G}{n} \cdot \frac{\partial \rho_{\text{spherical}}}{\partial \xi} dy \right| d\xi, \quad (18)$$

where d is the distance from the sound source to the measurement point.

By inputting a sweep signal into ℓ in Eq. (18) and plotting the resulting change in $|\bar{\theta}|$ as a function of ℓ , the red curve in Fig. 6 is obtained. Note that the numerically calculated data presented in this section were computed using arbitrary parameter values; Specifically, a density amplitude $\hat{\rho} = 1$, a distance $d = 1$ m, a frequency $f = 1$ kHz, and a time $t = 1$ sec., unless otherwise noted.

Fig. 7. Illustration of a laser beam interacting with spherical waves.

The red curve in Fig. 6 was found to asymptotically converge to a constant value as $\ell \rightarrow \infty$, indicated by the black dashed line in Fig. 6. The underlying reason for this convergence behavior can be considered as follows: In the case of a spherical wave, multiple curved wavefronts intersect the laser beam path. Since the deflection of the laser beam is proportional to the cumulative density gradient along the laser beam path, interference between these out-of-phase wavefronts leads to partial cancellation of the deflection effects as illustrated in Fig. 7.

Taking this fact into account, let the length L (hereafter referred to as the deflective length) represent the path length of the portion where the laser beam is actually deflected under the influence of the acoustic waves. Since the region of ℓ beyond the first intersection point (i.e., where the black dashed line intersects the red curve in Fig. 6) does not contribute to the overall deflection angle amplitude due to the cancellation of out-of-phase wavefronts, the value of L can be reasonably estimated to be near this intersection point.

Although the deflective length L is, in principle, numerically computable, the excessive computational cost renders it impractical for engineering applications. Therefore, to conceptually simplify and evaluate L more efficiently, an approximate expression is derived from the geometric interpretation in Fig. 7. Here, L represents the chord between two in-phase points on the spherical wavefront, corresponding to the region where amplitude cancellation due to out-of-phase wavefronts does not occur. Applying the Pythagorean theorem to this configuration yields:

$$L = 2 \sqrt{r^2 - d^2}. \quad (19)$$

Here, r can be expressed as

$$r = d + C\lambda, \quad (20)$$

where the dimensionless coefficient C serves as a scaling parameter that determines the extent of the deflective region in terms of wavelength, as shown in Fig. 7.

Incorporating Eq. (20) into Eq. (19) leads to the following expression,

$$L = 2 \sqrt{(d + C\lambda)^2 + d^2}. \quad (21)$$

Then, L was averaged in the same way as in Eq. (18), considering the effect of the beam width B_w :

$$\bar{L} = \frac{1}{B_w} \int_{d-\frac{B_w}{2}}^{d+\frac{B_w}{2}} 2 \sqrt{(\xi + C\lambda)^2 + \xi^2} d\xi. \quad (22)$$

Next, to determine the value of the coefficient C , the following procedure was performed. The convergent value of $|\bar{\theta}|$, which is obtained using the spherical wave model that represents jet noise, was substituted into the expression derived under the plane wave approximation, since the fundamental assumption of the measurement approach is based on the plane wave model as described in Sect. 3.1.

Taking the absolute value of the expression from substituting Eq. (1) into Eq. (2), the deflection angle amplitude of a laser beam passing through a plane wave is given by

$$|\theta| \approx \left| \frac{G}{n} \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} [\hat{\rho} \exp\{i(k\xi - \omega t)\}] \cdot \ell \right|, \quad (23)$$

and this result is plotted as the blue line in Fig. 6.

By replacing the path length ℓ in Eq. (23) with the averaged deflective length \bar{L} , the deflection angle predicted by the plane-wave model exactly matches the converged value obtained from the spherical-wave calculation. This point of agreement is marked by the black hollow circle in Fig. 6, and therefore the following equality holds:

$$\left| \frac{G}{n} \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} [\hat{\rho} \exp\{i(k\xi - \omega t)\}] \cdot \bar{L} \right| = \lim_{\ell \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{B_w} \int_{d-\frac{B_w}{2}}^{d+\frac{B_w}{2}} \left| \int_{-\frac{\ell}{2}}^{\frac{\ell}{2}} \frac{G}{n} \cdot \frac{\partial \rho_{\text{spherical}}}{\partial \xi} dy \right| d\xi. \quad (24)$$

A numerical evaluation of the above equation over the frequency range of 1–80 kHz yielded an average value of $C \approx 0.124$, with values varying within ± 0.001 . This variation corresponds to a maximum SPL deviation of 0.07 dB, indicating that C can be considered effectively constant for practical use in this measurement context.

Inputting $B_w = 2.12 \times 10^{-3}$ m and $C \approx 0.124$ into Eq. (22) yields the complete expression for averaged deflective length,

$$\bar{L} \approx \int_{\frac{z}{\sin\left(\frac{\varphi}{180}\pi\right)}^{-1.06 \times 10^{-3}}}^{\frac{z}{\sin\left(\frac{\varphi}{180}\pi\right)} + 1.06 \times 10^{-3}} \frac{\sqrt{(\xi + 0.124\lambda)^2 + \xi^2}}{1.06 \times 10^{-3}} d\xi, \quad (25)$$

where the distance d was replaced with the equation below,

$$d = \frac{z}{\sin\left(\frac{\varphi}{180}\pi\right)}, \quad (26)$$

which is geometrically derived under the assumption that the sound source is a point-like source located on the x -axis as illustrated in Fig. 4.

The averaged deflective length \bar{L} from Eq. (25) was substituted into Eq. (11) to calculate the sound pressure.

4.2. Compensation for influence of ambient light

A PSD outputs the intensity-weighted centroid coordinates of all incident light on its light-receiving surface. Therefore, when ambient light is also present, the output represents a biased average of the laser spot and the ambient illumination, as illustrated in Fig. 8. This results in a systematic measurement error, particularly in displacement-based estimations.

Assuming that the ambient light is uniformly distributed across the light-receiving surface, its centroid coincides with the geometric center of the surface. Consequently, the measured centroid displacement $s(t)$ becomes a weighted average

Fig. 8. Influence of incident ambient light.

Fig. 9. Setup for evaluating ambient light influence.

 Fig. 10. OASPL variation with radiant flux Φ .

of the laser beam's true centroid and the fixed center point of the ambient light distribution, thereby attenuating the true displacement in proportion to the intensity ratio.

To compensate for this effect, the experimental setup shown in Fig. 9 was constructed. Ambient light levels were measured using a power meter (LP1, Sanwa Electric Instrument), and an LED lamp was used to vary the illumination. The radiant flux Φ was set to 0, 25, 50, and 75 μW , while laser measurements were simultaneously performed using the existing system. Measurements were performed at four positions: $(x/D, z/D) = (0, 5)$, $(3, 3)$, and $(7, 7)$ for the over-expanded jet, and $(14, 4)$ for the ideally expanded jet. The obtained OASPL values were averaged across the four positions, and their variation is plotted as the red curve in Fig. 10. Based on the slope of this curve, a linear correction coefficient of approximately 0.032 dB/ μW was derived. Therefore,

Fig. 11. DOA of Mach waves from laser and sound intensity probe.

the corresponding correction term C_{AL} is derived as

$$C_{AL} = 0.032 \cdot \Phi, \quad (27)$$

and was incorporated into Eq. (14) to compensate for the influence of ambient light.

5. Validation

To validate the proposed technique, two experiments were conducted: one comparing directional accuracy with a sound intensity probe, and another comparing sound pressure estimation with a free-field microphone.

As a quantitative metric, the mean absolute difference (MAD), which indicates the average deviation between the two methods, was used for comparison. It is defined as

$$\text{MAD} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |DAT_{\text{laser},i} - DAT_{\text{ref},i}|, \quad (28)$$

where N is the total number of data points, $DAT_{\text{laser},i}$ denotes the i -th data point obtained from the laser measurement (either DOA, SPL or OASPL), and $DAT_{\text{ref},i}$ refers to the i -th reference data point measured by a free-field microphone or a sound intensity probe.

In addition, the Pearson correlation coefficient (PCC) was calculated to assess the linear relationship between the two sets of measurements. It is defined as

$$\text{PCC} = \frac{\text{cov}[DAT_{\text{laser}}, DAT_{\text{ref}}]}{\sigma_{DAT_{\text{laser}}} \cdot \sigma_{DAT_{\text{ref}}}}, \quad (29)$$

where $\sigma_{DAT_{\text{laser}}}$ and $\sigma_{DAT_{\text{ref}}}$ are the standard deviations of DAT_{laser} and DAT_{ref} , respectively, and $\text{cov}[DAT_{\text{laser}}, DAT_{\text{ref}}]$ is the covariance between the two variables. The PCC value ranges from -1 (perfect negative linear correlation) to $+1$ (perfect positive linear correlation), with 0 indicating no linear correlation.

5.1. Validation of sound direction measurement

To validate the proposed technique for DOA estimation, acoustic intensity vector measurements were conducted using a two-dimensional sound intensity probe comprising four parallel-axis 1/4-inch pressure microphones (46BG, GRAS

Fig. 12. SPL spectra of ideally expanded jet noise (top) and over-expanded jet noise (bottom), measured by laser and microphone.

Fig. 13. Enlarged view of peak frequency of screech tone.

Fig. 14. OASPL comparison between laser and microphone.

Sound & Vibration) arranged in a 1-inch aperture configuration. To accurately analyze the broadband noise captured by the probe, the phase and amplitude gradient estimator (PAGE) method was employed.²⁴⁾ Further methodological details are available in previous research by Gee et al.²⁵⁾

Figure 11 compares the DOA estimated by the laser measurement and the sound intensity probe, showing that the two methods exhibit broadly similar frequency characteristics. Across four measurement configurations at the same spatial location, the MAD between the two methods was 6.38° , indicating a high level of directional agreement. These results support the validity of the laser measurement for detecting the sound direction of supersonic jet noise.

5.2. Validation of sound pressure measurement

To validate the proposed technique for evaluating SPL, supersonic jet noise was measured using a 1/4-inch free-field microphone (Type 4939, Brüel & Kjær) mounted on a two-axis positioning system. The laser beam and the microphone were aligned to target the identical measurement point.

As shown in Fig. 12 (top), the broadband peak frequency of Mach waves generated by an ideally expanded jet was accurately captured. Similarly, Fig. 12 (bottom) illustrates that the sharp tonal peaks associated with screech tones from an over-expanded jet were clearly identified. An enlarged view provided in Fig. 13 further confirms that both the peak fre-

quency and SPL of the screech tones were precisely measured by the proposed technique. Furthermore, an average MAD of 0.499 dB and an average PCC of 0.9920 were obtained between the SPL spectra across these six measurement configurations at the same spatial location, indicating strong agreement between the two methods. Note that 1/12-octave smoothing was applied before calculating MAD and PCC to suppress spectral fluctuations and highlight overall trends.

Figure 14 shows the OASPL of supersonic jet noise measured at 50 arbitrary locations, where each point represents a pair of OASPL values obtained from the microphone and the laser measurement. The MAD between the two methods was found to be 0.337 dB for OASPL, corresponding to 0.243%, indicating strong agreement. In addition, a PCC of approximately 0.9991 confirms an excellent linear relationship between the two methods. These results validate the laser measurement technique as an accurate and reliable method for measuring the sound pressure of supersonic jet noise.

6. Conclusion

In this paper, an optical measurement technique was proposed to simultaneously measure both the sound pressure and direction of supersonic jet noise using a laser and a position-sensitive detector (PSD). Owing to its compact configura-

tion and non-intrusive nature, the method is well suited for aeroacoustic diagnostics in extreme environments where conventional microphones are impractical. The measurement methodology was developed through the following studies:

- The direction of arrival (DOA) of the acoustic waves was calculated from the deflected direction of the laser beam by performing principal component analysis (PCA) and applying a Butterworth band-pass filter.
- To accurately calculate the sound pressure level (SPL) from the deflection angle of the laser beam, the concept of deflective length was introduced and derived numerically based on wavefront geometry.
- The systematic error caused by ambient light was compensated through an experimental calibration method.

The proposed technique achieved a mean absolute difference (MAD) of 0.337 dB in overall sound pressure level (OASPL) and 6.38° in DOA, indicating excellent accuracy and consistency in supersonic jet noise measurements.

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